

IN-SITU SYNCHROTRON X-RAY MICROTOMOGRAPHY OF VOID EVOLUTIONS DURING NANOPOROUS NETWORK-ENABLED OUT-OF-AUTOCCLAVE MANUFACTURING OF AEROSPACE-GRADE WOVEN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This study presents in-situ synchrotron X-ray computed tomography (SRCT) of the void evolution and resin infusion behavior during a nanoporous network (NPN)-enabled out-of-autoclave (OoA) manufacturing process for aerospace-grade woven composite laminates. During the OoA process, the NPNs could facilitate gas evacuation and promote resin infusion into the interlaminar regions via the induced high capillary pressure. To better understand the underlying mechanisms of the NPN-enabled OoA process, a custom experimental setup employing a thermoelectric module was developed, which allowed active “freezing” of the resin flow during CT scanning while providing heating to promote resin flow between scans. After initial proof-of-concept tests on a lab-scale X-ray micro-CT system, the custom setup was used to scan IM7/8552 woven laminates with and without polymer aerogel NPNs at various stages of a typical composite cure cycle. These scans were conducted using SRCT at the HEX beamline of the National Synchrotron Light Source II (NSLS-II). In these in-situ scans, the baseline laminate exhibited significant void formation and coalescence at elevated temperatures due to volatile release and insufficient resin pressure. On the other hand, the laminate with polymer NPNs showed uniform resin infusion into the interlaminar regions and minimal void development. These results provided direct evidence of the critical role of NPNs in void mitigation during the NPN-enabled OoA process by maintaining open pathways for gas venting and inducing high capillary pressure that promotes resin infusion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing of aerospace-grade thermoset composite structures heavily relies on the usage of autoclaves that supply external pressure and convective heating to cure the composite laminates and to achieve minimal void content [1–3]. However, autoclaves often impose significant energy consumption,

equipment cost, and geometric constraints on the manufacturing process for aerospace-grade composites [4]. To overcome these issues, an out-of-autoclave (OoA) manufacturing process utilizing the high capillary pressure induced by nanoporous network (NPN) materials was developed to achieve void-free aerospace-grade composites [5]. When placed at ply-ply interfaces, the NPN materials can provide a pathway for trapped gas to escape while also supplying high capillary pressure to assist resin infusion into the void-prone interlaminar regions (see schematic in Figure 1 (a)). Using this method, void-free unidirectional and woven composite laminates have been successfully fabricated using autoclave-grade prepregs with vacuum-bag-only (VBO) setups using NPNs including vertically aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and polymer aerogels (see Figure 1 (c)) [6–8]. To further understand the NPN characteristics required to enable this OoA manufacturing method, detailed characterizations of the capillary pressure and permeability of various NPN materials have been performed and subsequently informed a 1-D theoretical model developed to predict resin infusion speed in different NPN materials [7,9]. However, there are still many outstanding questions about how voids evolve, and resin infuses into interlaminar regions during the NPN-enabled OoA process as resin viscosity, volatiles, and void content evolve.

Figure 1: (a) Schematics (recreated from [5]) showing the mechanisms of capillary driven OoA curing of aerospace-grade composites enabled by the nanoporous networks (NPNs) and (b) a representative SEM image of the polymer aerogel NPN used in this study.

To obtain temporal information on the microstructure evolution of the composite laminates during the NPN-enabled OoA process, we developed an in-situ X-ray micro-computed tomography (X-ray micro-CT) experimental setup that can actively freeze the uncured laminates for stable and high-resolution CT scans at different stages of the cure cycles. Proof-of-concept experiments were first conducted on a lab-scale X-ray micro-CT to demonstrate the feasibility of this method. The same testing setup was then adapted for synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT). SRCT scans were performed for IM7/8552 woven laminates with a $[0^\circ]_5$ layup with and without polymer aerogel films as the interlayers using the High Energy Engineering X-Ray Scattering (HEX, 27-ID) beamline at the National Synchrotron Light Source II, Brookhaven National Laboratory. From the reconstructed scans taken at different time steps during a typical cure cycle, significantly different void evolution and resin infusion behavior were observed for the IM7/8552 laminates with and without polymer aerogel NPNs. For the laminate without NPN interlayers, voids can be seen emerging at elevated temperatures while the laminate with the polymer aerogel NPNs exhibited uniform resin infusion into the NPN interlayers without internal void development. The insights obtained from the in-situ SRCT scans will provide valuable learnings on the void evolution and resin infusion behavior during the NPN-enabled OoA process that can help provide a sustainable manufacturing method for high-quality void-free aerospace-grade composites.

2 MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Experimental Setup

To achieve in-situ observation of void evolution and resin infusion behavior during the NPN-enabled OoA process, the resin flow inside the uncured composite laminates must be “frozen” during X-ray CT scans to enable stable and high-resolution imaging. To achieve this objective, we developed a custom

setup (see Figure 2 (a, b)) where a thermoelectric module is used to either heat the laminate to trigger resin flow or cool the laminate to “freeze” any resin motion during imaging by switching the electrodes of the thermoelectric module. To achieve efficient heating/cooling, the thermoelectric module is mounted on an off-the-shelf heat sink that provides a stable temperature near room temperature on the bottom side of the thermoelectric module (see Figure 2 (b)). A sectioned aluminum T-bar is attached on top of the thermoelectric module to conduct heat away or towards the composite laminates while also serving as a rigid and flat surface for the composite layup. Thermal paste was applied between the thermoelectric module and the aluminum support/heat sink to ensure efficient thermal conduction. The backside of the aluminum support was milled thinner to improve the transmission of the X-ray. A K-type thermocouple was mounted on the backside of the aluminum support to measure real-time temperature, which was used as input for a PID temperature controller that controls the heating/cooling of the thermoelectric module. Since the aluminum support provided a rigid and flat surface for the composite layup, a typical vacuum-bag-only setup (see Figure 2 (b)) was used which included all the necessary components, such as cork dams, caul plate, breather, vacuum port, and vacuum bag, and could accommodate laminates with a size of 0.5 inch × 0.5 inch (12.7 mm × 12.7 mm). In this study, all scans were performed on 5-ply $[0^\circ]_5$ IM7/8552 woven laminates. Two sets of laminates were imaged, the baseline samples without any NPN interlayers and laminates with polyimide aerogel films of ~50 μm nominal thickness (supplied by Aerogel Technologies, LLC) as NPNs at every ply-ply interface. Once the layup is completed, the setup is placed on the rotating sample stage for X-ray micro-CT or SRCT imaging (see Figure 2 (c)).

Figure 2: (a, b) Image and schematic showing the experimental setup for in-situ X-ray micro-CT inspection of void evolution within composite laminates during the curing process, and (c) test setup for SRCT at the High Energy Engineering X-ray Scattering (HEX, 27-ID) beamline, National Synchrotron Light Source II

2.2 In-situ X-ray micro-CT and SRCT procedures

Using the custom setup, in-situ X-ray CT imaging was performed using both lab-scale X-ray micro-CT (ZEISS Xradia 620 Versa) and SRCT at the Brookhaven National Laboratory using National Synchrotron Light Source II's High Energy Engineering X-ray Scattering (HEX, 27-ID) beamline. The lab-scale X-ray micro-CT experiments were conducted using the X-ray parameters of 160 keV voltage and 24 W power, with optics being a 4× objective and an HE2 filter. The optics and detector were positioned to result in a 1.6 μm voxel size. To prevent entanglement of the various wiring and vacuum hose, fan scans from -110 to 110 degrees were conducted with 3201 projections and an exposure time of 17 seconds, making the total scanning time roughly 15 hours without considering additional time for stage movement and taking reference scans. For SRCT tests, an X-ray energy of ~70 keV was used with the HEX beamline's optical module B setup, giving a voxel size of 1.3 μm and a field of view of 4.2 mm × 4.2 mm with the high-resolution sensor (3200 × 3200 pixels). Due to the high brilliance of the Synchrotron X-ray light source, a significantly reduced exposure time of 0.375 seconds was used for all the SRCT scans. Fan scans were performed from -90 to 90 degrees with 2401 projections, making each scan last for ~15 minutes.

Figure 3: (a) Manufacturer Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC) for IM7/8552 prepregs and the modified cure cycle with a 3-hour hold at 60 °C and numbered circles indicate time steps where CT inspections were performed, (b, c) representative temperature profiles recorded during the in-situ SRCT experiments.

To monitor resin infusion and void evolution within the composite laminates during the NPN-enabled OoA manufacturing process, scans were carried out at different time steps during a typical cure cycle used for the OoA process (see Figure 3 (a)). A modified cure cycle previously used to achieve void-free IM7/8552 woven composite laminates using polymer aerogel NPNs [6] was used. Compared with the manufacturer-recommended cure cycle (MRCC), the modified cure cycle has an additional 1-hour hold at 60 °C to facilitate the gradual wetting of the NPNs, which allows trapped gas to escape via the open pathway provided by the NPN interlayers. Twelve key time steps (steps 0-11) were selected for SRCT scans, while only selected scans at steps 0, 2, 4, and 5 were conducted on the lab-scale X-ray micro-CT. During the test, the thermoelectric module was controlled by the PID controller with a temperature set

point of $-2.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to freeze the resin flow during CT scans. After each scan, the electrodes of the thermoelectric module were reversed to enable heating. The PID setting first allowed the temperature to rise quickly at a rate of $\sim 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to the previous temperature step before continuing with the modified cure cycle with either a temperature ramp with a $3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating rate or a temperature hold. Measured temperature profiles showed good agreement with the temperature set points with minor oscillations ($\pm 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) due to thermal lag between the aluminum support and the thermoelectric module.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Proof of Concept Results using a Lab-scale X-ray micro-CT

Using the custom in-situ setup, we first obtained 3D volumetric scans of the 5-ply $[0^{\circ}]_5$ IM7/8552 woven composite laminates with polymer aerogel NPNs using the lab-scale X-ray micro-CT. Scans were performed at steps 0, 2, 4, and 5. The representative slices taken from scans of step 0 (as-bagged) and step 4 (after holding 15 minutes at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) were compared side by side in Figure 4. In the step-0 scan, the polymer aerogel NPNs can be seen at the ply-ply interfaces, with only one larger void at the interlaminar region. The lack of large voids likely resulted from the open pathways provided by the NPNs for the trapped gas to evacuate to the edges of the laminates. After heating to $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the 15-minute hold, the voids observed in the step-0 scan disappeared. The thickness of the porous NPN layers was also significantly reduced due to resin infusion into the polymer aerogel NPNs. As a result of resin redistribution, a reduction in laminate thickness from $\sim 1.3\text{ mm}$ to $\sim 1.1\text{ mm}$ was also observed. Through proof-of-concept experiments using the lab-scale X-ray micro-CT, we successfully demonstrated that high-resolution and stable scans can be achieved using our custom in-situ setup to monitor resin infusion and void evolution.

Figure 4: Representative slices taken from reconstructed volumes scanned at step-0 and step-1 for a 5-ply $[0^{\circ}]_5$ IM7/8552 woven laminate with polymer aerogel NPNs at every interlayer.

3.2 Void Evolution Observation from SRCT Results

After the successful in-situ observation of resin infusion and void evolution using the lab-scale X-ray micro-CT, we performed SRCT scans using the same setup at 12 time steps (see Figure 3(a)) during the modified cure cycle for 5-ply IM7/8552 $[0^{\circ}]_5$ woven laminates with and without polymer aerogel NPNs. Selected slices taken from steps 1, 5, 7, and 9 for both the baseline laminate and the laminate with polymer aerogel NPNs were shown in Figure 5. For the baseline laminate, small and medium-sized ($<100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) voids can be observed at the early stage of the cure cycle (step-1, see Figure 5 (a)). These voids are likely air bubbles trapped during the composite layup process. After ramping to $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and holding for one hour, significantly larger voids ($\sim 200\text{-}500\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) appeared (see Figure 5 (c)). The void expansion and coalescence may be attributed to the combination of lower resin viscosity and release of

volatiles from the prepregs at elevated temperature [10]. These voids further developed after the 3-hour hold at 60 °C (see Figure 5 (e)), as part of the resin between the fiber tows migrated to fill the intralaminar voids. Once the temperature reached 110 °C (see Figure 5 (g)), large voids with boundaries partially following the contour of fiber tows were observed. These results showcased the difficulty of obtaining void-free aerospace-grade composites without the external pressure supplied by an autoclave. Compared with the baseline laminate, the one with polymer aerogel NPNs exhibited minimal voids throughout the time steps scanned. Small voids present in the early stage of the cure cycle (see Figure 5 (b)) disappeared during the 60 °C hold as the NPNs provided open pathways for the gas to escape and were not fully saturated even after 1 hour at 60 °C (see Figure 5 (d)). After the 3-hour hold (Figure 5 (f)), the NPN layers were fully saturated with resin, and a surface void developed as the resin migrated to fill the intralaminar voids within fiber tows. No significant change in void morphology was observed after the temperature ramp to 110 °C (see Figure 5 (h)).

Figure 5: Selected slices from scans at various time steps showing void evolution for (a, c, e, g) the baseline 5-ply $[0^\circ]_5$ IM7/8552 woven laminate and (b, d, f, h) the laminates with polymer aerogel at every interlayer; dashed lines marked the upper and lower surface of the laminates.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we developed a novel in-situ X-ray tomography setup to monitor resin redistribution and void evolution during the NPN-enabled OoA manufacturing of aerospace-grade composites. Using the thermoelectric module-enabled custom setup, high-resolution and stable volumetric scans of IM7/8552 woven laminates with and without polymer aerogel NPNs were successfully obtained throughout key curing stages using both a lab-scale X-ray micro-CT system and the SRCT using the HEX beamline at NSLS-II. The obtained scans provided time-resolved insights into the resin redistribution and void evolution behavior during the OoA process. Compared with baseline laminates that exhibited significant void formation and coalescence, the laminates with polymer aerogel NPNs demonstrated superior void mitigation and uniform resin infusion into the interlaminar regions. These findings, together with our prior studies on theoretical modeling and measurement of key NPN characteristics, advanced our understanding of mechanisms behind the NPN-enabled OoA manufacturing of void-free aerospace-grade composites and could inform the development and sustainable manufacturing of various aerospace-grade composite systems.

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